

Spectrophotometric determination of nitrogen dioxide in the environment

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In the present investigation a simple, sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method for the determination of nitrogen dioxide in air has been described. The air sample containing nitrogen dioxide is passed through the absorbing solution of acidified potassium iodide to liberate iodine. The liberated iodine reacts with leucocrystal violet (LCV) to form crystal violet dye, which is measured at 590 nm. The proposed reagent has ~99% collection efficiency and stoichiometric ratio of $\text{NO}_2 : \text{NO}_2^-$ is 0.74. Beer's law obeyed over the concentration range of 0.1–1.0 μg of nitrite per 25 ml (0.004–0.04 ppm). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $1.54 \times 10^6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.000044 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The method has been applied for the determination of nitrogen dioxide in laboratory air, autoexhaust and cigarette smoke.

Several analytical methods for the determination of nitrogen dioxide such as chemiluminescence¹, photoacoustic spectroscopy², tunable diode laser³, laser induced fluorescence⁴, gas chromatography⁵, liquid chromatography⁶, ion chromatography⁷ etc. are reported. Spectrophotometric methods based on Greiss reaction have also been reported in the literature for the determination of nitrogen dioxide⁸. Many reagents such as *p*-nitroaniline, gluaiacol⁹, 8-hydroxyquinoline¹⁰, 1-aminonaphthalene-2-sulphonic acid¹¹, *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine, *p*-aminoacetophenone and oxalic acid¹² reported from this laboratory, have been useful for the determination of NO_2 .

The present communication reports a simple and sensitive method for the determination of nitrogen dioxide using a chromogenic reagent leucocrystal violet (LCV). The proposed method is based on the liberation of iodine by the reaction between absorbing solution (KI + HCl) and nitrogen dioxide present in air. The liberated iodine that oxidises LCV to form crystal violet was having absorption maxima at 590 nm. The proposed reagent has ~99% collection efficiency. The stoichiometric ratio of $\text{NO}_2 : \text{NO}_2^-$ is 0.74, which is in agreement with values in the literature¹³.

Results and discussion

The absorption spectra of the crystal violet dye showed a maximum absorbance at 590 nm. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range 0.1–1.0 μg of nitrite per 25 ml (0.004–0.04 ppm). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $1.54 \times 10^6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.000044 cm^{-2} respectively.

The precision of the method was verified by seven replicate analysis of 1.0 μg of nitrite per 25 ml for a period of seven days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.0097 and 2.16% respectively.

The collection efficiency was determined by passing air containing nitrogen dioxide through two impingers connected in series, each 10 ml of absorbing solution at flow rate 0.5 L/min. The results show that the proposed reagent has ~99% collection efficiency in the first impinger. It was observed that collection efficiency of the first impinger decreases with the increase of flow rate. The stoichiometric factor¹⁴ which is the ratio of absorbance of nitrogen dioxide to nitrite is found to be 0.74 by the present method.

10 ml of absorbing solution, 1 ml of LCV, ~3–4 drops of sodium hydroxide were sufficient for maximum colour development. The full colour development required 20–25 min and developed colour was stable for several days. Most suitable temperature range is 40–45° for the colour reaction. Above and below this temperature the colour intensity gradually decreased. Maximum absorbance value was obtained in the pH range of 4.0–4.5. Higher pH severely affected the stability of the dye and at lower pH colour development did not take place.

The effect of diverse ions commonly found with nitrogen dioxide was studied by adding known amount of diverse ions into the absorbing solution before sampling. Interference from sulphur dioxide and heavy metals was masked with 1 ml of 1% solution of hydrogen peroxide

and EDTA respectively. Carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, ammonia, formaldehyde and phenol, which are present in air with nitrogen dioxide, have no effect on colour development.

Conclusion :

The present method for the determination of nitrogen dioxide is simple sensitive and avoids the use of hazardous chemicals. This method can be compared favorably with the reported methods (Table 2). The method can be successfully applied to the trace determination of nitrogen dioxide in air and is suitable for field monitoring.

Experimental

Apparatus : A Systronics 106 digital spectrophotometer and a Systronics 335 pH meter were used. For air sampling, Midget impingers of 35 ml capacity were used and flow rate was controlled by rotameter.

Reagents : All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled deionised water used throughout the experiment. Standard sodium nitrite (E. Merck) solution. 1 mg ml⁻¹ of nitrite and 1.0 ml of chloroform was added as a stabilizer¹⁵. Working standard solution was prepared daily by dilution of stock solution. 1% Aqueous solution of potassium iodide (E. Merck). Leucocrystal violet (LCV-Eastman Kodak Co.)-LCV solution was prepared by dissolving 25 mg of LCV in 0.3 ml of 85% phosphoric acid and diluting to 100 ml with distilled water. This solution was stable for six months when kept in amber coloured bottle. Absorbing solution was prepared by mixing 7 ml of potassium iodide and 1 ml of HCl (6.0 M) and diluting the contents to 10 ml with distilled water. 1.0 M aqueous solution of NaOH was used.

Procedure : For preparation of calibration curve, nitrogen dioxide was prepared by bubbling purified air through fresh nitrite solution as described by Nash¹⁶. An aliquot of a solution containing 0.1 to 1.0 µg of nitrite was taken in an impinger. Nitrogen dioxide was liberated from the aliquot by adding 5 ml of 6.0 M hydrochloric acid dropwise from a microburette. The liberated nitrogen dioxide was absorbed in the absorbing solution taken in two midget impingers of 35 ml capacity each containing 10 ml of absorbing solution connected to a source of suction. The air was passed through the solution at a rate of 0.5 dm³/min for 15 min. The solutions of the two impingers were mixed. Then 1 ml of LCV and ~3-4 drops of 1.0 M sodium hydroxide were added. The contents were kept on water bath for 2-3 min at 40-45° and was left for 20-25 min at RT for the complete colour development of final solution.

Table 1. Determination of nitrogen dioxide in various samples

Sample	Total NO ₂ found (µg)		
	Present method	Reported method ¹¹	
Laboratory air (5 L)	A	0.67	0.65
	B	0.89	0.85
	C	0.93	0.87
Cigarette smoke (with filter)	A	0.41	0.39
	B	0.37	0.35
	C	0.53	0.52
Cigarette smoke (without filter)	A	0.49	0.47
	B	0.67	0.64
	C	0.79	0.75
Autoexhaust (scooter)	A	0.39	0.37
	B	0.36	0.36
	C	0.43	0.41

* Mean of three replicate analyses.

Application of the method :

In air : Proposed method was applied for the determination of nitrogen dioxide in polluted air. Known amount of nitrite solution was treated 1 ml of 6.0 M HCl which liberated the nitrogen dioxide. An air sampling train was fitted in laboratory. In this two impingers containing 10 ml of absorbing solution was connected to a source of suction. The air was sampled at the rate of 0.5 dm³/min for 10 min. The aliquots of absorbing solution were then analysed by the present and reported method¹¹ (Table 1).

In cigarette smoke : Smoke from various brands of cigarettes with and without filter was drawn through three midget impingers connected to air sampling train. The first two is containing acidic potassium permanganate (2.5% KMnO₄, w/v in 2.5% H₂SO₄) for oxidation of nitric oxide to nitrogen dioxide and the third impinger containing 10 ml of the absorbing solution¹⁷. The cigarette was marked at the required butt length The lighted cigarette was fixed in the glass holder and the air was sucked at the rate of 0.25 dm³/min till the marked length. After sampling the absorbing solution were mixed and aliquots were then analyzed by the present and reported method¹¹ (Table 1).

In autoexhaust : Nitrogen dioxide present in autoexhaust was drawn through the two midget impingers each containing 10 ml absorbing solution and attached to a air sampling train. After sampling the absorbing solution were mixed and aliquots were then analysed by the present and reported method¹¹ (Table 1).

Table 2. Comparison with other spectrophotometric methods

Sl. no.	Reagents/Ref.	Range (ppm)	λ_{max}	Remarks
1.	Sulphanilic acid + naphthylamine ⁸	0.05–1.20	520	Cu ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺ and strong oxidants interfere
2.	PNA + guaiacol ⁹	0.03–0.15	505	Extractive SO ₃ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ are interfere
3.	8-Hydroxyquinoline PNA ¹⁰	0.07–0.49	570	Extractive, Cu ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺ are interfere
4.	<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline + 1-amino-naphthalene-2-sulphonic acid ¹¹	0.08–0.64	545	Extractive, less sensitive
5.	<i>p</i> -Aminoacetophenone + NEDA + oxalic acid ¹²	0.12–0.96	548	Heavy metals and SO ₂ are interfering
6.	Potassium iodide + HCl + LCV (present method)	0.004–0.04	590	Simple more sensitive no interference of Cu ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺ and heavy metals

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